

CHANGES IN THE AGRICULTURAL AND INDUSTRIAL SPHERES OF UZBEKISTAN

G`oziyeva Aziza Abdusalomovna

Tashkent Medical Academy, Termiz branch, Faculty of Medicine No. 1, deputy dean for
work with young people

Abstract. In this article, based on the analysis of the main indicators of agricultural production, the current state of development of the agricultural sector is revealed. Information about the adoption of the strategy for the development of agriculture of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2020-2030 is provided, the main tasks of strategic priorities and the results achieved on them are highlighted.

Relevance of the topic. Agriculture for Uzbekistan is one of the most important areas ensuring economic growth, employment and income of the population. In recent years, the industry has demonstrated steady growth rates of 5-6%; agriculture provides 27% of employment in the economy as a whole. Agricultural lands occupy 45% of the territory of the republic, about 50% of the total population belongs to the rural population. The development of the agricultural sector in the republic occurs in parallel with significant organizational and economic transformations, which create favorable conditions for the development of new types of agricultural production and agribusiness, as well as the widespread use of innovative technologies. The need to implement innovative processes in the agricultural sector is associated, first of all, with the main problem of the economy - the rational use of limited (especially land and water) resources to meet the growing needs of society. At the same time, an equally important prerequisite for the innovative development of the agricultural sector is that today, in the context of globalization and fundamental changes in the world market, competition is intensifying, and it is innovation that is the most effective means of competition, as it leads to a reduction in production costs, increasing volumes and increasing the efficiency of agricultural production.

Research objective and methods. During the research and writing of the article there were methods such as economic and statistical analysis, observation, the method of expert assessments were used, monographic, etc.

Result. Today, as a result of the implementation of the priority tasks that were identified by the government of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the country has ensured sustainable effective development of almost all spheres of the economy. In particular, the implementation of program measures to reform and develop agriculture, aimed at ensuring food security, improving the quality of agricultural products and the export potential of the industry, provided a solid basis for achieving high indicators of agricultural development. Thus, in 2018, the share of agriculture in Uzbekistan's GDP amounted to 32.4%, the total volume of products (services) of agriculture, forestry and fisheries amounted to 199,537.4 billion soums, or 100.3% by 2017, in including in crop production and livestock farming, hunting and the provision of services in these areas - 193,703.3 billion soums (100.2%), forestry - 4,757.5 billion soums (103.1%), fisheries - 1 076.6 billion soums (113.8%).

In strategically important areas where regulatory functions are necessary, a clear separation will be established between the functions of government regulation and service provision; - increasing the efficiency of government spending on agriculture through the gradual redistribution of government financial resources aimed at providing key government services and implementing structural change programs; - strengthening the institutional capacity of government bodies in order to increase efficiency and effectiveness in managing public finances in the agri-food sector;

- improving communication

between funding research with the priorities and needs of the real sector and effective knowledge dissemination mechanisms;

- development of a modern education system aimed at increasing the competitiveness of agricultural producers and agribusiness;

Conclusion. Thus, in 2017-2020, grandiose reforms were carried out in the agriculture of Uzbekistan, the results of which have already made it possible to ensure sustainable growth of the industry and increase resource efficiency. In the future, they will serve to fully utilize the existing potential of the republic in agricultural development and bring Uzbekistan among the world leaders in the production and export of agri-food products.

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